

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11175127>

DESIGN PROJECT OF MODERN STUDENT DORMITORY

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ABSTRACT

The topic discussed in this article provides information on the usual and current trends in architectural facilities. Also, the topic discussed in this article is a solution to a current problem for students: the lack of living space, the inadequacy of existing hostels, the complete unsuitability of the provided living space and related problems. Also, the design of a modern dormitory for students is discussed.

Key words: *Architecture, object, dormitory, student housing, project, co-working, perspective, exterior, design, floor plan, facade.*

INTRODUCTION

Before talking about this topic, I would like to talk briefly about architecture. Architecture is one of the ancient and elegant spheres of human activity, its history goes back to the distant past. A person appears to be looking for a place to live. It builds a shelter for itself to be free from various external factors and dangers. This is the basis for the creation of architecture by itself. It is known to us from historical sources that people lived in rocks and caves in ancient times [1]. As humanity develops, they build better houses for themselves and start living in more and more comfortable conditions. This development has not stopped even now. People are looking for ways to improve their lifestyle by making various innovations.

It can also be said that architecture means the highest stage of construction, that is, high-level construction. In this sense, “architect” is close to the Uzbek word “architect”. That is why the term architecture is widely used in relation to architecture. Architecture is the highest level of construction art, but not every building can be equaled or compared to architecture. Because construction is a very comprehensive word and includes some areas that are not suitable for architecture. For example, construction of railways, construction of underground pipelines or mines, etc. So, not every construction can be architecture, but the basis of any architecture is, first of all, construction. In order for a building to become architecture, it must be created in the style of a high-level example or work of art. Architecture differs from other types of practical human activity, including construction, in that, in addition to utility issues, it also performs an ideological and artistic aesthetic task that meets the needs of a specific historical and socio-spiritual environment and era [2].

Architecture satisfies the material and spiritual needs of a person. It consists of the necessary parts of the means of living and recreation of the human society (residential houses, public buildings, gardens and parks, boulevards, etc.) production enterprises) are also included. In a general sense, architecture is a system of artificially formed material environments designed for practical and spiritual needs for human existence and activity. At the same time, architecture is also an art. Therefore, in architecture, a certain way of life, the thinking and demand of the time, certain aesthetic and ideological needs, a set of ideas finds its material and artistic expression [3].

Here, we will get acquainted with the project of a modern student dormitory, which is one of the architectural objects that combines the opportunities for people to live, relax, work, and get an education. How is it possible to have so many possibilities in one place? It is natural for all of us to have such a question, because nowadays the term “student dormitory” means only a building intended for students to relax and prepare for their classes. In addition, all student dormitories in our country have many problems related to lack of space, lack of necessary resources and other situations. This proposed project can provide a solution to all problematic situations and allow the

student to feel as if he is living in the dormitories of the world's most prestigious universities. In addition, there will be an opportunity to work without leaving this building. Other advantages of the project are detailed below.

METHODS

The research study on the proposed project of a modern student residence research methods. Here are some key methods used in the study:

Site visits: The researchers will visit the selected location for the project, study the location, study its climate, population, transportation infrastructure, and thus shape the project.

Literature review: Existing literature on architecture, studying student dormitories, their norms and standards to acquiring knowledge and skills about them.

Case studies: The researchers analyze case studies of successful dormitories from other regions to identify best practices that can be applied in this project.

These methods are utilized to collect data, understand the current state of the architectural environment, and propose recommendations for effective organization of the modern dormitories in Uzbekistan.

RESULTS

People create the project of the space necessary for human life and activity and build it. This process is different in various periods. Previously, projects were drawn on paper, but now this process is carried out using modern technologies. It is the same in construction, if before all the flow was done by human labor, now it is done by various technical means, and people just need to control it. Architectural objects are also being designed in accordance with the requirements of the times through modern methods, leaving aside the traditional ones. Take a look at this student dormitory project as an example.

According to the data, there are 173 student dormitories in Tashkent, and they can accommodate 47,400 students. But in the conditions of Tashkent, this is very little, not even 40% of those who need a bedroom. Around 75,000 students live in rented

accommodation. One can talk for hours about the problems of finding a rental, renting a property, and paying rent every month. In order to eliminate such problems, new laws are being developed under the chairmanship of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev and work is being carried out to implement them [4].

The head of our state has developed a program for the establishment of “Student houses” in Uzbekistan in 2021-2023. On September 9, 2021, a government decision was made on the construction of residences for students on the basis of public-private partnership. According to the decision, a total of 228 student residences (400 beds) will be built across the republic. Of these, the construction of 47 student residences in 2022, 67 in 2023, 62 in 2024, and 52 in 2025 is planned [5].

In order to solve such problems, I aimed to create a proposal project for a new modern student dormitory. I think that in the near future the problems of student housing will be completely solved. This project meets all the requirements in terms of construction and design. The project was developed based on construction regulations. This building adds beauty and grace to the city of Tashkent. Currently, Uzbekistan is strengthening social, economic and political relations with many foreign countries. Radical changes are also observed in the field of education. Student residences are also important in attracting foreign students, or establishing student exchange between universities and institutes. This proposal is intended for the residence of not only students of our country, but also foreign students. In the following places, we will take a closer look at the student housing project.

Figure 1. Front view of the proposed project.

At these paces, we can see the perspectives of the traditional student accommodation in our country and the proposed project in a new, modern interpretation. The task is almost the same, but the external design and capabilities are different. If we talk about the project, the building consists of a basement and 5 floors. Structural solutions are developed based on the function of the building. In addition, the project was designed in accordance with all the requirements of “Norms and rules of urban planning” and “Building codes and regulations”[6].

In the basement, the rooms of the student dormitory designed for sports, workshops, and technical rooms have been designed. Natural light is provided. On the first floor there is a "Co-working" center and rooms that must be in the student dormitory. The co-working center mainly consists of offices, which students can rent and use for the type of activity they want. The main purpose of designing the student bedroom in this way is to provide students with work, self-financing, and based on the above-mentioned decision.

Student bedrooms are designed from the second floor of the building. On this floor, there are rooms designed for students to prepare food, eat, relax, and prepare for lessons. rooms designed for preparation are placed. In this project, the bedrooms are taken as cells, and one cell consists of 2-3 bedrooms, a toilet and a bathroom. Dormitories are divided into 1-bed, 2-bed, 3-bed and 4-bed depending on their class. Retractable floor: The rest of the floors of the building under construction, i.e. 3-4-5 and 6th floors are considered to be reversible floors, and the rooms are placed on the upper floors in the same way as the 2nd floor was designed.

Front view. When processing the style part, it is necessary to create an appearance suitable for the surroundings. Many sketches were prepared and the building was given a completely new modern look. Since there are residential areas and a large road around the building, it was considered necessary to create a landscape area. A special landscape composition was created around the building based on Uzbek national ornaments.

Figure 2. Front view.

I came to the conclusion that the design solution is not complicated, it does not create an aggressive state when people see it, easy shapes are used, and it is advisable to use colors that are well adapted to the nervous system and not to exaggerate the color.

Figure 3. Perspective views.

If we pay attention to the entrance of the building, it is light colors used. Equipped with modern equipment. Installed above The lamps add brightness to the interior. On the left side of the entrance to the building is the reception area. There is room for two staff. One of them deals with the registration of those who come to the student dormitory, and the other deals with those who come to the "Coworking" center. A place with soft furniture is reserved in the center of the lobby for servants and visiting guests. Around the furniture, plants are also used, which give cleanliness to the interior design and the environment. The color chosen for the furniture is also very suitable for

the interior of the building. Every guest who enters the building should feel highly comfortable, for this purpose it is necessary to design on the basis of ergonomic requirements during the design process. The size of the large windows used in the building gives the building a special beauty by providing natural light.

Figure 4. Interior views

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I believe that it is preferable to design architectural objects as modern and multi-functional as this project. In this project, not only external design, but also convenient planning, the possibility of high energy saving of the building, and resistance to various emergency situations are important. In addition, with the initiatives of our President, great importance has been attached to the establishment of student dormitories, and new laws are being developed and work is being carried out to put them into practice. I think that in the near future the problems of student housing will be completely solved. A large number of such positive works is a sign that a wide path is being opened for young people who are our future. I would like to say about the project that if this project is put into practice, it will add beauty and grace to the city.

REFERENCES:

1. Sh. Abdullayev “History of Architecture” Publishing house named after Cholpon, Tashkent - 2018
2. “Fundamentals of architectural design” under the general editorship of Kh. Polatov “PUBLISHER” Tashkent - 2010
3. http://lib.jizpi.uz/pluginfile.php/18909/mod_resource/content/0/Arxitekturaviy%20loyihalash%20asoslari%20%281%29.pdf
4. https://fayllar.org/pars_docs/refs/1010/1009016/1009016.pdf
5. <https://abt.uz/blog/talabalar-yotoqxonasi-haqida>
6. <https://mc.uz/gradostroitelnye-normy/>